

On the Study of Polyhalides Part IV. Formation and Dissociation of Polyhalides of Ammonium and Substituted Ammonium Bases.

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Although some of the stable polyhalides of ammonium and substituted ammonium bases were known for a long time, no systematic work on equilibrium or solubility relation appears to have been made (cf. Johnson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1878, **33**, 397) Tinkler (*ibid.*, 1908, **93**, 1611), Rae (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **45**, 1725), Chattaway and Hoyle (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 654) prepared and studied the properties of the compounds of the type $N\cdot(Alk)_4 Hal_n$ (where n is 3, 5, 7 or 9) but neither the degree of dissociation nor the heat of formation was studied Reade and collaborators (*ibid.*, 1923, **123**, 143; 1924, **125**, 157, 1926, 2529) studied the preparation of a large number of quarternary ammonium polyhalides, Gray and Dakers (*Phil Mag.*, 1931, **11**, 81) prepared and measured the diamagnetism of polyhalides of Me_4N , Et_4N , etc With a view to obtaining quantitative information regarding the various polyhalides of ammonium and substituted ammonium bases, the present investigation was undertaken.

In the present paper, the formation and dissociation of chlorodibromide, chlorodi-iodide, fluorodi-iodide, bromodi-iodide, tri-iodide and polybromide of ammonium, bromodi-iodide of ethylpyridinium, tri-iodide of tetramethylammonium and tribromide of tetramethylammonium were studied by means of the solubility method. The solubility of bromine in ethylpyridinium bromide and that of iodine in tetraethyl bromide and iodide and in ethylpyridinium iodide have also been determined but the formation of the complex polyhalide can not be deduced from the results.

The method adopted for the determination of the solubility was similar to that described in the previous part of this series (Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 115). Any change in the solubility of halogens in presence of different cations or in the degree of dissociation of the halides in presence of dissolved halogens was neglected. It is further assumed that any complex polyhalide that might be formed is dissociated electrolytically almost to the same extent as the simple halide and behaves in all respect like the simple halide ion.

From the increased solubility of the halogens in the solutions of the different halides studied, it may be concluded that the increased solubility is due to the combination of a part of dissolved halogen with the halogen ion of the halide forming the polyhalide. Attempts to apply the law of mass action to systems like these can not be expected to succeed and there is no reason to suppose that the formation of any particular polyhalide represents the sole action at any particular concentration. However, over a certain range of concentration, the value of the equilibrium constant, calculated on the assumption that trihalides are formed, are found to be fairly constant. In the case of the reactions between bromine and bromides, the equilibrium constant calculated on the assumption of the formation of the tribromide is found to vary widely but better results are obtained by calculating on the assumption of the formation of the pentabromide, though the results are by no means constant. In the case of pyridine-ethyl bromide and tetraethylammonium bromide, the equilibrium constants calculated on the assumption of the formation of tribromides or pentabromides do not give a constant value owing probably to the fact that various other polybromides are formed to a more or less extent. This agrees with the fact that the tendency to the formation of higher polyhalides is greater in the case of complexes where all the halogen atoms are of the same kind (Ray, *loc. cit.*).

Owing to the reaction between bromine and fluoride, the solubility could not be determined. The reaction between iodine and fluoride was studied by the solubility method and an approximately steady value for the equilibrium constants were obtained although Carter and Hoskins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 580) could not determine the solubility owing to the reaction between iodine and fluoride. Tinkler (*loc. cit.*) also found no change in the ultraviolet absorption spectra of iodine by the addition of (Na, K or NH_4F) and concluded that probably no combination took place between iodine and fluoride. The present investigation, though does not give any constant value for the equilibrium constant, indicates that probably some combination takes place between iodine and fluoride. In the case of tetraethylammonium bromide and iodine and pyridine-ethyl iodide, a red precipitate was formed on the addition of iodine and the solubility of iodine was depressed. From this it appears that the compound precipitated contains most of the iodine that had dissolved in the water and is probably the required halide. Bromodi-iodide of pyridine-ethyl gave a black, viscous and

oily liquid on the addition of iodine though in these cases the solubility was not depressed. In the case of tribromides of pyridine-ethyl and tetraethylammonium bases, the peculiar fact was noticed that on the addition of bromine a yellow precipitate gradually dissolved and in this case also the solubility was not depressed. Here as has already been pointed out the values of the equilibrium constant was by no means constant. Definite conclusions regarding the peculiarities noticed could not be drawn without further work.

The results of the investigations are given in the following tables. The degree of dissociation of the halides were calculated, unless otherwise mentioned, from the equivalent conductivities as given in the International Critical Table of Physical Constants.

TABLE I.

Formation of NH₄ClBr₂. Temp., 25°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of Br ₂ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K.
4·0N	0·65	1·98 g/10 c.c.	3·47
2·0	0·70	1·26	3·80
1·0	0·74	0·87	4·71
0·5	0·77	0·60	4·70
0·25	0·80	0·46	4·70
0·125	0·84	0·39	4·74
0	—	0·30	—
			Mean 4·716*

TABLE II.

Formation of NH₄ClI₂. Temp., 25°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K
4·0N	0·65	0·02 g./10 c.c.	2·58
2·0	0·70	0·01	2·57
1·0	0·74	0·01	2·56
0·5	0·77	0·007	2·58
0·25	0·80	0·006	2·76
0·125	0·84	0·005	2·76
—	—	0·03	—
			Mean 2·576

* In calculating mean values, only those values which are nearly constant were considered.

TABLE III.

Formation of NH₄BrI₂. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K.
4.0 N	0.68	0.33 g./10 c.c.	32.99
2.0	0.73	0.10	17.33
1.0	0.76	0.05	16.79
0.5	0.79	0.02	16.58
0.25	0.81	0.01	16.68
0.125	0.84	0.01	16.61
0.0625	0.88	0.007	16.69
0	—	0.003877	—
			Mean 16.67

TABLE IV.

Formation of ammonium polybromide. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of Br ₂ in sat. sol.	Equilib. const. K (Calc. as Br ₃).
4.0 N	0.68	3.37 g./10 c.c.	12.33
2.0	0.73	1.28	9.34
1.0	0.76	1.21	8.46
0.5	0.79	0.91	8.20
0.25	0.81	0.76	8.00
0.125	0.84	0.69	7.98
0.0625	0.88	0.65	7.41
0	—	0.30	—
			Mean 8.165

TABLE V.

Formation of NH₄I₃. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₄ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K.
4.0 N	0.69	2.89 g./10 c.c.	454.6
2.0	0.76	1.62	443.0
1.0	0.78	0.79	428.3
0.5	0.80	0.40	426.2
0.25	0.82	0.21	425.7
0.125	0.85	0.11	427.6
0.0625	0.88	0.05	427.8
0.03125	0.91	0.03	426.9
0	—	0.003	—
			Mean 427.1

TABLE VI.

Formation of NH₄Et₂. Temp., 25°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K.
4.0 N	0.37	0.031 g./10 c.c.	4.79
2.0	0.49	0.014	2.70
1.0	0.58	0.009	2.34
0.5	0.65	0.006	2.19
0.25	0.73	0.005	2.10
0.125	0.79	0.004	2.50
0.0625	0.85	0.004	2.50
0	—	0.003	—
			Mean 2.394

TABLE VII.

Formation of (CH₃)₄NI₃. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K.
N/10	0.67	0.0026	—
N/20	0.72	0.0029	—
N/40	0.77	0.0046	10.98
N/60	0.79	0.0046	16.09
N/80	0.81	0.0044	15.59
N/100	0.82	0.0043	15.48
N/120	0.84	0.0042	15.39
N/160	0.85	0.0041	15.43
0	—	0.0038	—
			Mean 15.47

TABLE VIII.

Solubility of I₂ in (C₂H₅)₄NI. Temp., 25°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln.
N/10	0.62	0.0027 g./10 c.c.
N/20	0.72	0.0028
N/100	0.80	0.0029
N/200	0.82	0.0031
N/500	0.84	0.0032
0	0	0.0038

TABLE IX.

Solubility of I₂ in (C₂H₅)₄NBr. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln.
N/2	0.29	0.0018 g./10 c.c.
N/4	0.31	0.0021
N/8	0.33	0.0029
N/16	0.34	0.0033
N/32	0.35	0.0035
N/64	0.36	0.0036
0	—	0.0038

TABLE X.

Solubility of I₂ in C₅H₅N·C₂H₅I. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc. ...	N/2	N/4	N/8	N/16	N/32	N/64	0
Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln. (g./10 c. c.). ...	0.0015	0.0016	0.0017	0.0017	0.0018	0.0027	0.0039

TABLE XI.

Formation of polyhalides of (C₂H₅)₄NBr. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of Br ₂ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K (calc. as Br ₂).
N/2	0.29	0.28 g.	6.03
N/4	0.31	0.37	6.03
N/8	0.33	0.34	6.06
N/16	0.34	0.32	6.13
N/32	0.35	0.32	13.43
N/64	0.36	0.31	14.20
0	—	0.30	—

Mean 6.08

TABLE XII.

Solubility of Br₂ in C₅H₅N·C₂H₅Br. Temp., 25°.

Halide conc. ...	N/4	N/8	N/16	N/32	N/64	N/128	0
Solubility of Br ₂ in sat. soln. (g./10 c.c.) ...	0·10	0·11	0·31	0·31	0·32	0·31	0·31

TABLE XIII.

Formation of C₅H₅N·C₂H₅BrI₂. Temp., 30°.

Halide conc.	Degree of dissociation.	Solubility of I ₂ in sat. soln.	Equilib. const. K.
N/2	0·82	0·0099 g./10 c.c.	3·90
N/4	0·84	0·0069	3·70
N/8	0·89	0·0055	3·71
N/16	0·91	0·0047	3·73
N/32	0·93	0·0043	3·72
N/64	0·94	0·0041	3·85
0	—	0·0038	—

Mean 3·770

Degree of dissociation of (C₂H₅)₄NBr and C₅H₅N·C₂H₅Br were determined experimentally from conductivity measurements; the results are given in Tables XIV and XV.

TABLE XIV.

Degree of dissociation of (C₂H₅)₄NBr. Temp., 25°.

Dilution.	Conductance specific.	equiv.	Degree of dissociation.
2,000	0·0186	36·32	0·29
4,000	0·0099	39·50	0·32
8,000	0·0052	41·76	0·34
16,000	0·0027	43·06	0·35
32,000	0·0014	43·87	0·35
64,000	0·0007	45·22	0·36

123·70^a^a Calculated from the mobility of (C₂H₅)₄N and Br-ions.

TABLE XV.

Degree of dissociation of C₅H₅N·C₂H₅Br. Temp., 30°.

Dilution.	C o n d u c t a n c e.		Degree of dis- sociation.
	sp.	equiv.	
2,000	0·0460	92·00	0·82
4,000	0·0235	95·10	0·85
8,000	0·0124	99·70	0·89
16,000	0·0064	103·00	0·92
32,000	0·0032	104·80	0·94
64,000	0·0016	106·70	0·95
128,000	0·0008	107·00	0·96
256,000	0·0004	109·40	0·98
		112·00*	

The compound C₅H₅N·C₂H₅Br was found to be extremely hygroscopic. In determining the specific conductance, every possible precaution was taken to dry the substance but the results obtained are not probably extremely accurate although sufficiently reliable for the present purpose.

From the preceding tables, it will be observed that the value of the equilibrium constant of the same complex ion varies with the nature of the cations as has already been pointed out (Ray, *loc. cit.*). Thus the present work also concords with the observation that the linkage between the halogen atoms of the complex is of an electrostatic nature (*cf.* Ray, *loc. cit.*).

The authors desire to express their thanks to Dr. P. Neogi for his kind interest in the work.

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Received April 25, 1936.

* Calculated by extrapolation.